

Effect of herbs with anti-inflammatory activity on mastalgia and engorgement: a systematic review and meta-analysis

Efecto de las hierbas con actividad antiinflamatoria sobre la mastalgia y la congestión mamaria: una revisión sistemática y un metanálisis

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Abstract

Introduction: Administration of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAID) has shown promising results in improving mastalgia and congestion, although it was associated with side effects. This study was conducted with the aim of investigating the effect of medicinal herbs with potential anti-inflammatory activity on periodic mastalgia.

Methods: The search strategy was systematic screening of English electronic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, ISI Web of Science, Cochrane Library with no time restriction from inception to March 1, 2023. Jadad scale was used to assess the quality of included articles.

Results: The findings of this analysis show that plant extracts with antioxidant potential can significantly re-

duce the severity of mastalgia compared to the control group SMD: 0.75 (-0.89 to -0.61; $p=0.01$; CI 95%)-also the heterogeneity index value is ($I^2=0\%$; $P = 0.5$). Evening primrose oil and Vitagnus can significantly reduce the severity of mastalgia in comparison with control.

Conclusion: Considering the importance of women's health, which plays an effective role in family functioning, and the fact that mastalgia can disrupt their activities, and on the other hand, medicinal plants with potential anti-inflammatory activity can have beneficial effects on the improvement of mastalgia. This method can be used as a useful method in improving periodic mastalgia.

Keywords: Mastalgia, anti-Inflammatory, herbs, meta-analysis.

Introducción y antecedentes. La administración de antiinflamatorios no esteroides (AINE) ha mostrado resultados prometedores en la mejora de la mastalgia y la congestión, aunque se asoció con efectos secundarios. Este estudio se realizó con el objetivo de investigar el efecto de las hierbas medicinales con potencial actividad antiinflamatoria sobre la mastalgia periódica.

Métodos. La estrategia de búsqueda fue una revisión sistemática de bases de datos electrónicas en inglés, incluidas PubMed, Scopus, ISI Web of Science y Cochrane Library, sin restricción de tiempo desde el inicio hasta el 1 de marzo de 2023. Se utilizó la escala de Jadad para evaluar la calidad de los artículos incluidos.

Resultados. Los resultados de este análisis muestran que los extractos de plantas con potencial antioxidante pueden reducir significativamente la gravedad de la mastalgia en comparación con el grupo de control SMD: 0,75 (-0,89 a -0,61; $p = 0,01$; IC 95%) -también el valor del índice de heterogeneidad es ($I^2 = 0\%$; $P = 0,5$). El aceite de onagra y Vitagnus pueden reducir significativamente la gravedad de la mastalgia en comparación con el grupo de control.

Conclusión. Teniendo en cuenta la importancia de la salud de la mujer, que desempeña un papel eficaz en el funcionamiento familiar, y el hecho de que la mastalgia puede alterar sus actividades, y por otro lado, las plantas medicinales con potencial actividad antiinflamatoria pueden tener efectos beneficiosos en la mejora de la mastalgia. Este método puede utilizarse como un método útil para mejorar la mastalgia periódica.

Palabras clave: Mastalgia, antiinflamatorios, hierbas, metanálisis.

Mastalgia¹, and breast engorgement are common problems of reproductive age. They are the reason for women's referring to clinics. The rate of these problems in different studies has been reported to be 70%¹. Mastalgia can be divided into two major categories including cyclic pain and non-cyclic pain². This pain is followed by symptoms such as congestion, pain, burning, heaviness, and bilateral breast tenderness in the premenstrual period³. Mastalgia causes anxiety and worry about the possibility of breast cancer in patients. Also, patients with unnecessary and frequent referrals to clinics and performing various diagnostic methods such as mammography and biopsy impose much financial burden on the healthcare system⁴. Cyclic mastalgia is mostly seen between the ages of 20 and 30. However, some women experience it after menopause⁵. Three primary causes for cyclic mastalgia have also been reported to be increased estrogen, decreased progesterone, and increased prolactin, decreased ratio of unsaturated fatty acids to saturated acids, and the role of inflammatory mechanisms such as increased levels of inflammatory biomarkers such as alpha-1 and alpha-6 Interleukin, and tumor necrosis factor-alpha⁶. The breasts were normal on clinical evaluation. A combination of supportive care, appropriate bra support, and non-hormonal drugs such as evening primrose oil and vitamin B6 may be recommended as first-line treatment. Anti-estrogen therapy for 3 to 6 months is the second line of treatment. Danazol may be used in treatment-resistant cases. Many women with mastalgia do not want to continue these treatments due to the adverse effects of treatments such as bromocriptine, tamoxifen, or gonadotropin-releasing hormone analogs⁷.

Breast engorgement is the result of fullness and firmness of the breasts. It is accompanied by complaints of mastalgia and sensitivity. Primary breast engorgement is due to interstitial swelling and the beginning of abundant milk production. It occurs mostly between 24 and 72 hours after delivery with a normal range of 5 to 7 days. The mean peak of symptoms is 3-5 days after delivery. Both drug and non-drug methods are considered useful for treating breast engorgement. To solve this problem, it is recommended to use hot and cold bags and bras at appropriate sizes⁸. Moreover, the efficacy of treatments such as acupuncture, acupressure, massage, oxytocin spray, breast lymphatic drainage treatment, and compressed cabbage leaves has been proven. Oral analgesics such as ibuprofen and acetaminophen are beneficial for 12-24 hours. Oral NSAIDs, acetaminophen, and ibuprofen provide promising outcomes in the area of mastalgia and breast en-

gorgement⁸. The NSAID should be administrated under supervision based on scheduled days for the patients to avoid serious side effects in toxic amounts⁹. Adverse side effects of NSAIDs include ulcers, internal bleeding, kidney failure, increased risk of heart attack, and stroke⁹.

The consumption of medicinal plants and herbal medicines has increased in recent years. Many studies have investigated the effects of herbal medicines on women's problems, especially in recent years¹⁰. Some medicinal plants have anti-inflammatory properties, such as flax seed⁶, chamomile^{11,12}, Nigella sativa¹³, Vitex agnus¹⁴, and cinnamon¹⁵. The literature review indicated that a systematic review has been conducted so far to investigate the beneficial effects of medicinal plants with potential anti-inflammatory activity on cyclic mastalgia and breast engorgement as two common problems of women. Thus, this systematic review investigated the effect of medicinal plants with potential anti-inflammatory activity on cyclic mastalgia and breast engorgement.

To conduct this review, Latin electronic sources such as PubMed, Scopus, ISI Web of Science, and Cochrane Library were systematically searched without time limitation until March 1, 2023. Two researchers independently reviewed electronic sources. Non-agreement cases were reviewed and resolved by a third party. The following keywords were used:

(Mastalgia or Breast Pain or Breast Pains or breast engorgement) and (herbal or herbal medicine or chinese traditional medicine or phytotherapical or Vitex agnus-castus or chaste or flaxseed or isoflavones or Matricaria chamomilla or chamomile or Nigella Sativa or Cinnamon). Also, other references from related original and review articles in these databases were searched and analyzed.

Study selection process

Endnote-6 software for resource management was used to organize the studies. After searching the database and other sources, all the articles and sources were entered into the endnote software, and duplicate articles were removed. Then, the title and abstract of the articles were reviewed. The articles not related to the research were removed. The full text of the remaining articles was reviewed based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Finally, the studies that met the

inclusion conditions of the study were included in the study. Two researchers selected the articles independently. In cases where there was a lack of agreement, a consensus was achieved by the participation of a third researcher. Inclusion criteria included: 1- Studies with a clinical or quasi-experimental trial structure that investigated the effectiveness of medicinal herbs with potential anti-inflammatory activity with a placebo on women with mastalgia and 2- The study should have a control group including placebo or periods without drug treatment.

Exclusion criteria

- 1- The summaries of articles presented in conferences, review articles, editor's notes, letters, and case reports
- 2- The studies that used the combination of herbal and chemical drugs in the treatment group
- 3- Using topical and oral chemical treatment in the treatment group
- 4- Mastalgia has been reported as one of the symptoms of premenstrual syndrome.

Figure 1. PRISMA statement¹⁶

Data extraction Table

The research team designed the data extraction Table, and two researchers reviewed each of the articles of this study independently. In the case of misunderstanding, a consensus was achieved by the participation of the third party. Table 1 presents the title, author's name, year of publication, number of people in the group receiving herbal medicines and control, type of herbal medicine and control, women's age, drug dose, treatment duration, measurement tool, severity of mastalgia, side effects, outcome, and general results of the study.

Table 1. Specifications of the studies included in the present systematic review article

Author/year/country	Age	Intervention (dose and duration of treatment)	Comparison (dose and duration of treatment)	Results studies
Molazem, 2016, Iran ¹⁷	36.31	Vitex Agnus Castus (40 mg a day as single dose,) /for three menstrual cycles.	Meloxicam (15 mg/day) Placebo for three menstrual cycles.	mastalgia decreased in VAC group v.s placebo
Saghafi et al., Iran, 2018, ¹⁸	Chamomile Group=26.7/ Placebo group/29.6	The chamomile group (n=26; five drops three times a day) for two consecutive months	Placebo group (n=29; five drops three times a day) for two consecutive months	A Significant decrease In Chamomile group compared with placebo Groups
Gharaiy et al., iran, 2017 ¹⁹	cinnamon group =26.2 y/ Placebo group =25.76 y	cinnamon group (n=37;400 mg of cinnamon) three capsules per day / two months	Placebo group (n=37) three capsules per day / two months	A Significant decrease in cinnamon group compared with placebo groups (p=0.02).
Mirmolaei et al., Iran, 2017 ³	Nigella Sativa group=38.5 y/ Placebo=40.1y	Nigella Sativa syrup (n =32;10 ml per days) for three months	Placebo (n=33;10 ml per days) for three months	A statistically significant decrease In Nigella Sativa groups than placebo
Jahdi et al., Iran, (2019) ²⁰	Evening Primrose Oil Group /39.88y Placebo Group =40.28y	one capsule of 1000 mg every 12 hours, (n=33)	Placebo every 12 hours (n=30)	EPO have the better therapeutic effects in the treatment of cyclical mastalgia
Dokoohaki et al., Iran, (2020) ²¹	35.62	2g/day of evening primrose for 6 months (n=25)	Placebo for 6 months (n=25)	A statistically significant difference between the two groups
Ingram et al., Australia, (2002) ²²	40.6y	Group 1 and = 80(n=7) or 40 mg (n=5) of Isoflavones, daily for two months	Placebo for two months (n=6)	The reduction in pain was 13%, 44%,31%. for placebo, 40 mg and 80mg
Pruthi et al., America, (2010) ²³	Over the age of 18 years	evening primrose (3000m g per day n=11) for six months	Placebo (n=11) for six months	Evening primrose and placebo had a similar p=0.18
Modoodi et al., Iran, (2020) ²⁴	15-49 years	10 ml of Vitagnus drop for three months (n=34)	8 ml of Placebo drop for three months (n=33)	A statistically significant difference between the two groups
Mirghafourvand et al., Iran, (2016) ²⁵	Flaxseed group=32.7 Vitex agnus group=32.6 Placebo group=32.6	25 g daily Flaxseed powder for two months (n=53) 3.2-8.8 mg of vitagnus daily for two months (n=53)	Placebo for two months(n=53)	Flaxseed and vitagnus were effective in reducing mastalgia in the short term
Sekhvat et al., Iran, (2009) ²⁶	Vitagnus group30.2y/ placebo=29.9y	60 drops of Vitagnus daily for three months; n=46	60 drops of placebo for three months; n=55	Vitagnus were more effective ness than Placebo

Quality evaluation Table

To evaluate each article, the article information was examined based on the Modified Jadad tool. This tool is a checklist containing eight questions evaluating different parts of the article. Question 1 is related to the randomization of samples in the study. If this is mentioned, the article will be given a score of one, otherwise, it will be given a score of zero. Question 2 is related to the proper and correct explanation of the randomization method in the article. If the randomization method is correct and inappropriate, it will receive the score -1, and if it is correctly mentioned, it will receive a +1 score, and if there is no explanation, a score of zero will be given to it.

Similarly, questions 3 and 4 are about blinding and expressing its appropriate method. It is scored similarly to randomization. Question 5 is about the description of the number of samples that have been removed from the study for some reason. If the number and reason for the removal from the study is mentioned, a score of +1 will be given, otherwise, a score of zero will be given to it. Question 6 is related to the correct and complete mention of the inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study. Question 7 is related to evaluating and mentioning the side effects caused by therapeutic intervention. Question 8 is related to the description of statistical methods. Similar to the previous ones, if it is mentioned, a score of +1 will be given to it, otherwise, a

score of zero will be given to it. If the study is double-blinded, it will be given a score of +1, and if it is single-blinded, a score of +0.5 will be given to it. The maximum score obtained from the Modified Jadad tool is 8. If the score is from 0 to less than 4, the article's level is considered weak, if it is from 4 to less than 6, its level is considered moderate, and if it is 6 or more, its level is considered strong. Two evaluators will independently evaluate the articles and review the summary and limitations of the article. Before reviewing the articles, the names of the authors and the journal will be removed from them. Several meetings will be held at the beginning of the study to compare the scores of the two evaluators. Before conducting the review, the Kappa coefficient of agreement between the two evaluators will be calculated. Finally, the Kappa agreement coefficient and its significance should be examined. If this coefficient is more than 80, the agreement between the observers is assumed to be good. If it is between 60 and 80, the observers should be trained again before starting the study. However, if there is a difference of opinion between the two evaluators, the third evaluator will make the judgment. If it is less than 60, another observer should be used Tables 2-4.

Table 2. Quality evaluation of articles based on the Jadad tool

Row	Was the research described as randomized?	Was the approach of randomization appropriate?	Was the research described as blinding?	Was the approach of blinding appropriate?	Was there a presentation of withdrawals and dropouts?	Was there a presentation of the inclusion/exclusion criteria?	Was the approach used to assess adverse effects described?	Was the approach of statistical analysis described?	total
Molazem ¹⁷	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	4
Saghafi et al. ¹⁸	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Gharaiy et al. ¹⁹	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Mirmolaei et al. ³	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Jahdi et al. ²⁰	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Dokoohaki et al. ²¹	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	8
Ingram et al. ²²	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	7
Pruthi et al. ²³	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Modoodi et al. ²⁴	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Mirghafourvand et al., Iran, (2016) ²⁵	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Sekhavat et al., Iran, (2009) ²⁶	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8

Table 3. quality of included studies assessed by Jada scale

Author	Randomization			Blinding			Report of dropping out	Total score
	Mention randomization	Appropriate Method	Inappropriate Method	Mention blinding	Appropriate method	Inappropriate method		
Monazzami et al., ⁸	*	*	-	-	-	-	*	3
Zolala et al. ¹⁵	*	*	-	*	*	-	*	5
Pruthi et al. ²³	*	*	-	-	-	-	-	3
Jahdi et al. ²⁰	*	*	-	-	-	-	*	3
Ingram et al. ²²	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dokoohaki et al., ²¹	*	-	*	-	-	-	*	3
Aydin et al. ⁵	*	*	-	-	-	-	*	3
Gharaiy et al. ¹⁹	*	*	-	-	-	-	-	2
Ghelichli et al. ¹¹	*	*	-	*	*	-	*	5
Hamood et al. ¹⁴	*	*	-	-	-	-	*	3
Naseri et al. ³⁵	*	*	-	-	-	-	*	3

Statistical analysis

Forest plots were analyzed using Comprehensive Meta-analysis software. Publication bias was examined using the Begg test. I^2 and Q of Cochran's test were used to report the heterogeneity index between studies. Also, heterogeneity was judged based on percentage and significance level. The existence of heterogeneity was judged based on a P -value less than 0.05. Values less than 25% of I^2 indicate low heterogeneity and values of 25-100% indicate moderate to high heterogeneity²⁷. A random or fixed effect model was used to report the data. If the heterogeneity level was high or significant, the fixed effect model was used instead of the random or fixed effect model to report the data. A p -value was used to examine the significance of the mean difference. A p -value of less than 0.05 was considered significant. A random effect model was used in this study due to the existence of methodological heterogeneity in the studies. In the forest plots, the square size indicates the number of samples in each study, the lines drawn on both sides indicate the effect size of each study at the 95% confidence interval.

The effect of c on cabbage compress on breast engorgement

In the first high-quality study, three groups including cabbage compress early breast care (CCEBC), early breast care (EBC), and general nursing breast care (GNBC) were compared in terms of mastalgia and breast firmness. Pain levels in both CCEBC and EBC groups were significantly lower compared to GNBC ($P < 0.05$) four days after delivery. Breast firmness in the CCEBC group was significantly lower than in the EBC and GNBC groups. There was no significant difference among the three groups regarding breast skin temperature¹¹. In the second study by Gagandeep et al., cabbage leaves were placed on the breasts of patients for thirty minutes three times a week. Breast consistency and breast tenderness were reduced significantly in the cabbage leaf group compared to the control group receiving routine care in patients with breast engorgement¹⁸. A third study was by Gharaiy et al., cabbage leaves were placed on the breast of patients for 15-20 minutes three times in 24 hours. The effect of cabbage leaves was more effective than the control group in relieving breast engorgement (routine care)¹⁹. In the study by Aydin et al., mastalgia (Mean difference of $p = 0.005$) and breast firmness (mean difference of $p = 0.003$) decreased significantly in mothers

of the cabbage leaf group compared to mothers of the gel pack group⁵.

In the study by Jahdi et al., women with breast engorgement received a hot compress for one week and cold cabbage was placed on the breast for one week. The effect of combined treatment (cold cabbage leaves in hot compress) and hot compress alone both had similar effectiveness in reducing breast engorgement in mothers suffering from postpartum breast engorgement²⁰. In Dokoohaki et al., study, both cold cabbage leaves ($p = 0.05$) and hot compress ($p = 0.001$) were effective in relieving breast engorgement in postpartum mothers. However, both groups showed similar effectiveness²¹. In the study by Ingram et al., both cabbage leaf treatment and hot and cold compresses were similarly effective in relieving breast engorgement in mothers with postpartum breast engorgement ($P = 0.07$), while hot and cold compresses were more effective than cold cabbage leaves in reducing pain ($P < 0.001$) in mothers with postpartum breast engorgement²². In the study by Pruthi et al., cabbage leaves ($p > 0.00$) and hot compress were effective in reducing mastalgia and breast engorgement. However, hot compress was more effective than cabbage leaf compress in relieving pain²³.

Alcea, ginger, and commiphora wightii compress on breast engorgement.

In the study by Hamood et al., patients with breast engorgement were divided into two groups. The first group received routine interventions and hot compresses before breastfeeding and cold compresses after breastfeeding. The second group received Alcea compress in addition to hot and cold compresses. However, the severity of breast engorgement in the group receiving the combined group (first group) was significantly lower ($P < 0.001$)¹⁴. In the study by Monazzami et al., the mean severity of total breast engorgement after intervention in the right and left breasts decreased in the ginger hot compress group and the control group. However, its effect on the severity of breast engorgement in the ginger hot compress group was significantly higher than the control group ($p < 0.001$)⁸. In the study by Zolala, in 60% of patients who had used the cream produced from the Alcea plant, compared to 22% of them, the score of the placebo cream for breast engorgement reached zero. The Alcea cream showed more effectiveness than the placebo cream ($P < 0.001$)¹⁵.

Analyzing the results of the Iranian herbal medicines revealed that the standardized mean difference between the two groups of herbal medicines with antioxidant properties and the control (-0.61 to -0.89; 95% CI) is -0.75, which is statistically significant ($p = 0.01$). Additionally, the heterogeneity index ($I^2 = 0\%$; $P = 0.5$) value between studies is zero (references in Diagram 2). These results indicate that plant extracts with antioxidant potential can significantly reduce the severity of cyclic mastalgia compared to the control group Figure 1.

The results revealed that the standardized mean difference between evening primrose oil and control groups (-1.06 to -0.409, CI: 95%) is -0.73, which is statistically significant (p=0.001) and the heterogeneity index value is zero Figure 2, indicating the protective effect of evening primrose oil.

The results of the analysis showed that the standardized mean difference between the Vitex agnus and control groups (-0.95 to -0.51, CI: 95%) is -0.73 see Figure 3 and this difference is statistically significant between the two groups (p=0.001) Figure 3.

Figure 1. shows the mean effect size individually and overall with a 95% confidence interval for studies comparing herbal medicines with antioxidant activity and control

Meta Analysis

Figure 2. The mean effect size shows individually and overall with a 95% confidence interval for studies comparing the effects of evening primrose oil and control.

Meta Analysis

Figure 3. shows the mean effect size individually and overall with a 95% confidence interval for studies comparing the effects of Vitex agnus and control

Meta Analysis

Based on our review, the present study is the first meta-analysis reviewed clinical trial studies to investigate the effectiveness of herbal medicines with antioxidant activity on cyclic mastalgia. Twelve articles were reviewed. Four studies were related to *Vitex agnus*, three studies were related to evening primrose oil, one study was related to flaxseed, one study on *Nigella sativa*, one study was related to cinnamon, one study was related to soya, and the last study was related to chamomile. The results indicate that herbal medicines with oxidant activity improve cyclic mastalgia compared to placebo. In addition, the sub-group of *Vitex agnus* and evening primrose oil have beneficial effects on improving cyclic mastalgia. In the present study, the reduction of pain severity in the cinnamon group was more significant than in the placebo group²⁸. Eugenol in cinnamon can prevent prostaglandin biosynthesis and be effective on inflammation²⁹. Herbal compresses with antioxidant properties such as cauliflower have had a noticeable effect in the treatment of breast engorgement.

Thymoquinone is one of the primary components of *Nigella sativa*. It probably has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, inhibits oxidative stress, strengthens the immune system, has anti-oxidation, anti-inflammatory, and antihistaminic properties¹⁰. The inflammatory process is regulated by lipoxygenase and cyclooxygenase. Inhibition of lipoxygenase and cyclooxygenase pathways prevents the metabolism of arachidonic acid and inhibits the production of prostaglandins and leukotrienes³⁰. Dithymoquinone, thymohydroquinone, thymol, thymoquinone, and compounds derived from *Nigella sativa* that can be involved in the general anti-inflammatory activity³¹.

A study investigated the anti-inflammatory effects of *Nigella sativa* on female rats suffering from experimental allergic encephalomyelitis. The results revealed that the anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and protective effects of *Nigella sativa* extract in a dose (200 mg/kg of body weight) reduce inflammatory factors and improve the inflammatory condition in rats suffering from experimental allergic encephalomyelitis³². A review study indicated that *Nigella sativa* oil extract and thymoquinone have anti-inflammatory impacts in experimental models of inflammation such as encephalomyelitis, colitis, peritonitis, and arthritis. *Nigella sativa* also exerts its effects by suppressing prostaglandin and leukotrienes, which are mediators of inflammation. In addition, *Nigella sativa* extract and thymoquinone reduce tumor necrosis factor-alpha, COX2, and interleukin-1 beta in pancreatic ductal cancer cells³³. A study on 72 women with cyclic mastalgia revealed that *Nigella sativa* could

reduce the severity of cyclic mastalgia compared with placebo³.

A study revealed that the reduction in pain severity was higher in the cinnamon group than placebo²⁸. Cinnamon extract can prevent the production of prostaglandins by inhibiting COX and can be involved in inhibiting inflammation³⁴. A study that investigated the anti-inflammatory effects of cinnamon extract reported that the oral consumption of cinnamon extract prevents the development and progression of intestinal colitis by inhibiting the expression of COX-2 and pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IFN- γ , and TNF- α)³⁴. A study included in this meta-analysis showed that flaxseed was better at reducing the severity of cyclical mastalgia than placebo²⁵. Consistent with human studies, studies conducted on animal models revealed that the hydroalcoholic extract of flaxseed has appropriate anti-inflammatory effects compared to NSAIDs such as salicylates³⁵. A study revealed that chamomile could significantly reduce the severity of cyclic mastalgia compared to placebo¹⁸. The pain-relieving effects of chamomile can be attributed to anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects so different compounds of chamomile have anti-inflammatory effects. Its Chamazulene has an anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effect, its apigenin has an anti-inflammatory effect, its flavonoid has an anti-inflammatory effect, and its α -bisabolol has anti-inflammatory effects³⁶. Its anti-inflammatory effects are mostly due to the compounds of matrixine (plant alkaloid), bisabolol (plant alkaloid), and its oxides³⁷.

In the study by Ketsuwan et al., the breast engorgement severity was reduced in two groups of herbal compresses (consisting of dried herbs such as ginger, acacia leaves, citrus peel, camphor, and salt) and hot compresses. However, the reduction in the breast engorgement severity was reported more in the herbal compress group. This result is consistent with the results of the present study³⁸. Ginger, cauliflower, and *Alcea* have antioxidant effects and can inhibit inflammatory compounds. The leaves of the *Alcea* plant also heal damaged tissues and improve various forms of inflammation⁸. Minghetti et al., found that ginger extract is absorbed through the epidermis and has an effective anti-inflammatory response on the mice's skin. They also concluded that ginger's anti-inflammatory effect might be through skin absorption and its transfer to the blood circulation³⁹. Ginger extract in hot water reduces the levels of prostaglandins and leukotriene (inflammatory mediators), reducing pain in gout patients⁴⁰.

Mastalgia and breast engorgement can disrupt their activities, and all herbal medicines with anti-inflammatory activity such as *Nigella sativa*, chamomile, flaxseed, *Vitex agnus*, and evening primrose oil can have beneficial effects on improving cyclic mastalgia. Herbal compresses with antioxidant properties such as cauliflower significantly affect the treatment of breast engorgement. These herbal medicines with anti-inflammatory properties can be used to improve cyclic mastalgia and breast engorgement. The results of these studies should be interpreted with caution due to the high heterogeneity between studies and their small sample size.

Limitations

One of the primary shortcomings of this study is the low methodological quality of some of the studies reviewed in this systematic review. It is better to design and report future studies based on consort. Another limitation of this study is the small number of studies, indicating the need for more studies with a larger sample size in this field. We should treat with caution in generalizing the results since most of the studies were conducted in Iran.

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